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The woman's researcher tale: A Review of Bibliometric Methods and Results for Studying Gender in Science

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1. Introduction

Gender self-identification plays a crucial role in shaping the opportunities and choices scholars make throughout their academic careers (Beddoes & Pawley, 2014). Women [1] often perceive their careers as hindered, while the image of the scientist as a man is socially elevated (Boekhout et al., 2021). This situation has led to an increasing demand for "solid quantitative support to what is intuitively known" (Larivière et al., 2013). Although bibliometrics have some limitations, they have become a valuable tool for analyzing the status of women in science, providing insights into patterns, trends and disparities.

Studies on gender inequality are highly politicized and need to be interpreted with care and a critical approach. For instance, there are cases where gender differences are not acknowledged or are simply denied. A well-known example is the Strumia study, which suggests biological differences as the reason for observed gender gaps (Strumia, 2021;

Andersen et al., 2021). The difficulty of generalizing within bibliometric research exacerbates this issue. Data limitations, an overreliance on descriptive analyses, and contradictory reports based on specific country or field case studies highlight these difficulties (Nygaard et al., 2022b). Most studies focus on Western countries, providing little evidence from other regions (Prozesky & Beaudry, 2019), and there are disciplinary biases, as most studies concentrate on STEM fields. Nonetheless, there is a consensus that gender differences are present in most aspects in academia, though causes behind these differences remain unclear.

There have been targeted literature reviews covering the broad scope of gender and bibliometrics, from approaches that focus on identifying gender and analyzing bibliographic data (Halevi, 2019) to studies on specific elements such as productivity and performance (Nygaard et al., 2022a), funding (Cruz-Castro et al., 2022), the citation gap (Wu, 2024) and gendered specialties during education (Alers et al., 2014), among other aspects. The present narrative review aims to provide a comprehensive and updated examination of the use of bibliometric methods to study gender differences in science and their results. This review distinguishes itself from previous literature by addressing both the methodological challenges and substantive findings related to gender disparities in scientific research. Our goal is to summarize the main methodological advancements in studying gender using bibliometric methods, outline the key findings, identify existing gaps, and suggest directions for future research.

This narrative review covers research on bibliometric analyses that focus on gender from the last 30 years (1993-2024). We have covered 253 publications, included in the references, which we have divided into two main sections that structure the review. Firstly, a methodological part focuses on the main issues addressed by bibliometric techniques in gender studies, including a section on causality. Although this is not strictly bibliometric, it is key to discuss it as it affects the validity of bibliometric gender studies. The second section focuses on gender differences in research activities, underlying mechanisms behind these differences, and the overall effects of gender inequality, as reported by bibliometric studies. To provide an overview of the narrative review we include a discussion section, integrating findings from

different studies and highlighting any convergences and divergences in the results. We conclude by discussing the limitations of current methodologies and findings to propose a future research agenda with potential directions to address the identified gaps.

This work offers several novel contributions to the field. First, it examines a wide range of methodological approaches, from traditional descriptive analyses to the combination with more recent techniques such as gender assignment or refined designs for identifying causality. This provides a comprehensive overview of the tools available for studying gender disparities. Second, it offers a global perspective on gender inequality in science by considering studies from diverse regions. Third, it includes a detailed examination of gender disparities across various disciplines, highlighting both the unique challenges faced by women in STEM fields and the commonalities across different research fields.

2. Methodological approaches

Studies on gender inequality face a series of methodological challenges crucial for interpreting their findings, such as gender assignment based on metadata, selection of the unit of analysis and issues related to claims of causality, biases or differences in gender. This section will delve into how these have been solved in the literature.

2.1. Gender assignment

Here we explore two key aspects when assigning gender: the metadata needed from bibliographic records to infer gender, and the algorithmic approaches followed for assigning gender to authors.

2.1.1 Metadata. Data on gender is usually unavailable in bibliographic metadata, thus studies infer them from indirect metadata. Usually, the metadata used to infer gender is authors names. Thanks to the inclusion of full names in bibliometric databases, researchers' gender can be estimated, showing the probability that a name corresponds to a particular gender. For instance, Web of Science introduced full names in 2007 (searchable since 2011) and a linkage of authors and affiliations in 2008. Other databases commonly used in gender studies include arXiv (Holman et al., 2018), PubMed

(Andersen et al., 2020), ProQuest (Liu et al., 2023a), OpenAlex (Song et al., 2024) or Google Scholar (Andersen & Nielsen, 2018). For this gender inference, linkage between authors and affiliation is crucial, since, for instance, the name 'Andrea' is generally assigned to women except in Italy, where it is common among men. Moreover, the inclusion of last names enhances accuracy in some regions, such as Slavic countries.

This metadata is sometimes combined with other sources of information, such as pronouns used by authors for self-identification. Maliniak et al. (2013) and Azoulay & Lynn (2020) used this data to assign and validate gender. Another kind of metadata comes from surveying the researchers and asking them for their gender (Zheng et al., 2022) or asking the colleagues of the researchers in question (Amering et al., 2011). This is a more direct approach, but less common given the time-consuming nature and that it does not guarantee a complete dataset.

2.1.2 Methodological approaches for gender assignment. Depending on the metadata used, there are different methods to infer gender. As aforementioned, most methods for gender identification focus on given names as the primary means of assignment. These methods involve matching names against a pre-existing database containing a comprehensive collection of names associated with assigned genders or probabilities thereof. Refinements to this approach often incorporate geographical information derived from affiliation metadata, allowing for a more nuanced understanding and avoiding overgeneralizations.

Many studies use third-party algorithms (like GenderAPI) (e.g. Teich et al., 2022; Abramo et al., 2022) and only few develop their own methods for gender assignment using names (e.g. Jamali & Abbasi, 2023; Ma et al., 2023). To this aim, they use existing lists of names assigned to men or women in different countries such as the US Census (Larivière et al., 2013). While some algorithms provide binary classifications (e.g. Genderchecker), most offer the probability of a given name being assigned to a given gender (e.g. Genderize.io). Table 1 shows a non-comprehensive list of the most used gender assignment services and algorithms.

Table 1 *Non-comprehensive list of gender identification services.*

Algorithm	Information used (type of result)	Access	Regular Updates (last update)	Data sources	Size	Link
Gender API	Name (Percentage)	Private	Yes	Publicly available data, governmental data and manual additions/corrections	6,084,389 (190 countries)	https://gender-api.com/
Genderize.io (Ozan Soft)	Name (Percentage)	Private	Yes	Open to the general public government sources	4,079,646 (188 countries)	https://genderapi.io/ http://cran.r-nexus.com/web/packages/genderizeR/vignettes/tutorial.html
Gender Guesser (NamSor)	Name (Percentage)	Private	?	?	10,253,421,542 names	https://gender-guesser.com/
Gender-guesser (gender.c)	Name (Unknown, androgynous, female, male, mostly_female, mostly_male)	Public	No (2016)	Nam_dict.txt	44,568 names	https://pypi.org/project/gender-guesser/
NameAPI (Optimaize)	Name (Percentage)	Private	Yes	Phone books, national government publications, websites on the subject, local freelancers	590,000 (55 countries)	https://www.nameapi.org/
Gender-detector (Open Gender Tracking)	Name (Binary)	Public	No (2015)	Social Security Administration (USA) Office of National Statistics (UK) Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Administration (UK) Scotland General Register Office (UK)	125,000 (2 countries)	https://pypi.org/project/gender-detector/
Sexmachine (Python)	Name (Androgynous, male, female, mostly_male, mostly_female)	Public	No (2013)	Nam_dict.txt	44,568 names	https://pypi.org/project/SexMachine/#description

Gender (CRAN)	Name (Percentage)	Public	No (2011)	First names and dates of birth using historical datasets (U.S. Social Security Administration, the U.S. Census Bureau (via IPUMS USA), and the North Atlantic Population Project)	339,967 (from 1789-1930) 91,210 (from 1930 onwards)	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/gender/
Genni + Ethnea for the Authority 2009 dataset	Name (two methods: binary and Androgynous, male, female, mostly_male, mostly_female)	Public	No (2018)	Sex-machine data and US Social Security Administration	9,300,183 names	https://databank.illinois.edu/datasets/IDB-9087546
World Gender Name Dictionary	Name	Public	Yes	34 groups of national databases (full detailed list available on their Github)	25,000,000 names (195 countries/territories)	https://github.com/IES-platform/r4r_gender
Wiki-Gendersort	Name (Masculine, Femenine, Unisex, Initials, Unknown)	Public	No (2018)	Wikipedia (English) first names	694,376 names	https://github.com/nicolasberube/Wiki-Gendersort
Genderchecker	Name (Male, Female, Unisex)	Private	No (2011)	2001 and 2011 UK census data.	102,240 names	https://genderchecker.com/
Face++	Face (Binary)	Private	?	?	?	https://www.faceplusplus.com/

Another technique uses given names as input to search for pictures in search engines (Kong et al., 2022), or to retrieve individuals' images from their own personal or institutional websites (van den Besselaar & Sandström, 2017). Both approaches assume a relation between names or facial characteristics, and gender. Moreover, they adopt a binary stance of the researcher's gender: man, woman, or unknown if the information is unclear, which might obscure other gender identities leaving no room for self-identification. Lastly, because pronouns are not typically available in bibliometric databases, alternative sources such as personal websites or social media (e.g. X, LinkedIn) are used to retrieve this information (e.g. Campbell & Simberloff, 2022).

2.1.3 Key points and considerations. The predominant metadata utilized for gender inference is names. However, names may indicate perceived gender but will not provide information about legal or self-defined gender. This may make it look as if gender self-identification is the most accurate approach (Van Buskirk et al., 2022), however it is also the least exhaustive and most resource intensive. Some authors propose creating a self-declared gender identification database for each journal (Ribarovska et al., 2021), while others include disclaimers stating that the notion of “gender” used in their research does not refer to the authors’ self-identification (Kong et al., 2022).

Regarding the methodological techniques, it is important to stand out that they provide a binary idea of gender, although gender is not a binary category (Lindqvist et al., 2021). In this sense, the She Figures 2021 report highlighted the need to consider non-binary gender data (European Commission, 2021). Over the past decade, researchers have become more aware of how a binary conception of gender can bias their findings and the limitations of gender assignment algorithms (Halevi, 2019). However, these limitations are still not universally acknowledged.

Databases used by algorithms to create their lists of names are crucial for measuring their accuracy. For instance, Wikidata information may suffer from biases translated from Wikipedia, which overrepresents men (Tripodi, 2023; Zheng et al., 2023). Moreover, gender identification lists are not inherently global, thus some of these methodological approaches do not work well in certain Asian and Sub-Saharan African countries, or Brazil (Andersen et al., 2019; Larivière et al., 2013), potentially biasing the results and creating research gaps in these regions. Karimi et al. (2016) suggest using separate gender identification models for each language. Moreover, a researcher’s affiliation may not reflect their country of origin nor origin of their name (Boekhout et al., 2021).

Furthermore, many gender assignment algorithms are privately-owned, updated regularly and work relatively well, but they lack transparency and accessibility for many researchers (González-Salmón & Robinson-Garcia, 2024). Alternative and open methods tend to use smaller databanks, centered on English-speaking countries (e.g., Gender-detector, Genderchecker) and it is more likely they end up being abandoned (e.g., OpenGenderTracking Project, SexMachine), since creating an algorithm may ensure

transparency, but it is also time-consuming and not always possible. Efforts have been made to combine different approaches to overcome the inherent limitations of each method (e.g., Chan & Torgler, 2020; El-Ouahi & Larivière, 2023; Ma et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2023), which may be the most robust way to gain higher precision and exhaustivity in gender assignment (Karimi et al., 2016). However, using more refined and accurate gender assignment methods is more resource and labor intensive, which may explain why its use is not more widespread.

2.2. Unit of analysis

Choices regarding operationalization are crucial because certain publication practices appear to be influenced by gender. Results will vary depending on the unit of analysis observed, which refers to the object or sampling unit described by variables for making inferences (McGrath, 2005, p. 263) or describing. Here, we discuss the main units of analysis used in bibliometric research on gender: publications, authorship, individual researchers, and citations or references.

2.2.1 Publications. Researchers aim to determine how many publications are generated over a certain period by using them as a unit of analysis. But the operationalization of this unit varies across studies (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023). Some research looks at first authors to create a categorical variable, identifying a paper as written or led by women when they are first authors, and vice versa (Caplar et al., 2017). Variables can also include combinations such as male-male, female-female, male-female, and female-male when two first authors contributed equally (Broderick & Casadevall, 2019). Other approaches count papers multiple times, assigning as many genders to papers as there are authors (Kong et al., 2022), determine a percentage based on the number of men and women in the author byline (Ruggieri et al., 2021), or create a woman-to-man author ratio for each publication (Demaine, 2021).

2.2.2 Authorship. Gender assignment allows researchers to determine the gender of the authors of a publication, thus allowing an analysis of underlying gendered dynamics in authorship, basic for constructing indicators. For instance, the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University assigns gender to each authorship in their universities ranking, thereby measuring universities' gender

diversity and generating different types of indicators: the number of authorships at a university, the number and proportion of authorships belonging to women and men, and the number of authorships whose gender is unknown (Van Eck, 2019). Other studies use this unit of analysis to examine the gender composition of each authorship position (West et al., 2013), sometimes focusing on key positions such as first, last, and corresponding authorship (Bendels et al., 2018b).

2.2.3 Individual researchers. Researcher as unit of analysis implies carrying out an author name disambiguation as to group an individual researcher's outputs and information (Tekles & Bornmann, 2020). For example, Cameron et al. (2016) depart from a list of authors publishing in six journals from ecology and then link them to their Author ID using Scopus. In this way, they assess productivity differences between genders. Spoon et al. (2023) use a different approach, by retrieving individuals' career history from faculty census to study faculty retention in the United States.

By focusing on individuals as the unit of analysis, Holman & Morandin (2019) investigate gender homophily in collaboration patterns. On a similar line, Mihaljevic-Brandt et al. (2016) recreate publication histories of mathematicians using the zbMATH database and examine differences in collaborations patterns and research topics. Another perspective is followed by Chan & Torgler (2020), who use career-citation metrics (excluding self-citations) to look for gender differences in the academic success for highly cited authors. Conversely, Mishra et al. (2018) study the role of self-citations by gender. They do so by assigning gender to a list of highly productive authors and then computing the share of self-citations they produce. In this case they use a probabilistic disambiguation algorithm applied to publications in PubMed to identify the publication history of authors.

2.2.4 Citations and references. Another way to examine gender differences is to focus on citations as the unit of analysis. Here gender is assigned to papers or authors referenced by a core group of publications. For example, Wang et al., (2021), retrieved publications from 14 communication journals, extracted their list of references and identified the gender of first and last authors of cited publications. This allowed them to investigate gender differences in citation patterns. Dion et al. (2018) followed a similar

approach to investigate how the gender composition of fields would affect gender disparities in referencing patterns. That is, whether fields with a higher representation of women would produce a smaller gender citation gap. Another approach is that of Nettasinghe et al. (2021), who use the Microsoft Academic Graph and the list of publications from journals of the American Physical Society to create an author-citation networks to study citation disparities and the role of homophily and preferential attachment within and between genders and authors affiliated to highly ranked institutions in the Shanghai Ranking.

2.2.5 Key points and considerations. The choice of unit of analysis will allow studying different aspects related to gender in academia: differences in citation rates, productivity, career gaps, or differences among groups of authors. Declaring the unit of analysis and comparing findings with papers using the same approach, is key to avoid inconsistent comparisons across the literature. Nygaard et al. (2022b) refer to this as the distinction between the "what" and the "who," emphasizing the importance of avoiding comparisons between fundamentally different entities. Establishing a clear unit of analysis is essential to avoid errors like comparing results on productivity differences with citation patterns which will mislead any conclusion drawn from such analyses (McGrath, 2005). This lack of rigor may partly explain why some studies yield contradictory conclusions (Ceci et al., 2014; Nygaard et al., 2022b).

2.3. Causality, biases and differences

Most bibliometric studies combine both descriptive and causal approaches (e.g., Andersen et al., 2019; Bagues et al., 2014). However, some publications rely more heavily on descriptive analysis (e.g., Bendels et al., 2018a; Mason & Goulden, 2002), while others emphasize causal analysis (e.g., Ceci & Williams, 2011; Squazzoni et al., 2021). Various methodologies are used to analyze gender differences. Among the most common are regression analyses (Aksnes et al., 2019; Brommesson et al., 2022), counterfactual inference (Buchanan et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2020; Sarsons et al., 2021), matching techniques (Andersen et al., 2019; Frandsen et al., 2020), survival analysis (Hart et al., 2019; Kaminski & Geisler, 2012), scientific mapping (e.g., Bagdi et al., 2023), co-citation (e.g., Nguyen et al., 2021), logistic regression (e.g., Sebo et al., 2020), difference in

differences (DID) (Liu et al., 2022; Madsen et al., 2022), propensity score matching (Dorantes-Gilardi et al., 2023; Krapf et al., 2017) or cluster analysis (e.g., Sandström, 2009).

2.3.1 Key points and considerations. While gender differences are influenced by multiple factors (Ceci et al., 2014), studies often focus on specific causes while controlling for other variables. This approach can be challenging because control variables may not be fully independent, limiting the capacity of such analyses to “uncover mechanisms that produce the gender disparities” (West et al., 2013, p. 6), and masking potential mediation effects between different variables (Zheng et al., 2022). The issue is contentious since differences may not always lead to biases or disparities, and not all differences necessarily represent unfairness (Traag & Waltman, 2022). Generally, studies that go beyond descriptive analysis attempt to uncover gender differences related to biases, discrimination, and other factors (Boekhout et al., 2021), assuming that, even if not visible at plain sight, differences between men and women persist in academia, as they do in every other social environment.

3. Findings

Having explored the methodological approaches in the previous section, we now turn our attention to the specific findings of gender-focused bibliometric studies. Understanding where and how gender differences manifest in academic authorship, research activities, and professional opportunities is crucial for developing effective strategies to address these disparities. In the following section, we group papers based on the differences they identify, the factors that explain them, and the consequences arising from such disparities.

3.1. Gender differences

Firstly, research asks itself where gender differences occur in academia. Most studies reviewed below delve into this issue. Others try to go deeper and after confirming such differences, they try to locate how deep down they are entrenched in academia. Here we find studies looking to unveil such differences, and we divide them given their main focus.

3.1.1 Authorship. Authorship order decisions reflect entrenched social dynamics and exhibit gendered characteristics that perpetuate disadvantages for women in science (e.g., Demaine, 2021; González-Álvarez & Cervera-Crespo, 2017). It is important to consider that disadvantages for women's authorship vary by discipline. For instance, women's position and presence in the byline have not changed significantly despite their increasing presence in fields such as Economics (Boschini & Sjögren, 2007), Pediatrics (Fishman et al., 2017), or Medicine (Jagsi et al., 2006). Conversely, an increase in women in academia correlates with an increase in their overall authorship in other specialties, such as Dermatology (Feramisco et al., 2009).

In STEM fields women's disadvantage is more pronounced. Ghiasi et al. (2015) found that women constituted 20% of total authorship in Engineering. Mihaljević-Brandt et al. (2016) found that women publish fewer solo-authored publications in Mathematics, a field where single-authored papers are still common. Cavero et al. (2015) showed that women's authorship in Computer Science increased from 3% to 16% over 50 years (1966-2009), but they argued this positive trend might slow down. We also see this disadvantage in other fields, such as Life Sciences. Bendels et al. (2018b) showed that in the Life Sciences, Multidisciplinary, Earth & Environmental Sciences, and Chemistry categories from the Nature Index, women represented almost 30% of authorships.

While the gap has narrowed over time, women remain underrepresented as first authors in certain disciplines (Broderick & Casadevall, 2019; Colwell et al., 2020; Sidhu et al., 2009). For example, there is an overrepresentation of women in first author positions in medical fields such as Neuroscience, Neurology, or Psychiatry (Marescotti et al., 2022), while there is an underrepresentation in others such as Entomology (Walker, 2020). Additionally, countries with a higher overall proportion of women as first authors tend to have sharper first-authorship differences between fields, leading to a "gender equality paradox" (Thelwall & Mas-Bleda, 2020). Disadvantages are also observed in corresponding authorship. Even when women are first authors, they are less likely to be corresponding authors (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2025; Fox et al., 2018; Morillo et al., 2024). In difficult circumstances, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, men assumed a greater role as corresponding authors than women (Bell & Fong, 2021). However, studies here are limited and tend to be field-specific. This is not the case with last authorship,

where there is abundant and uncontested evidence pointing towards a disproportionate number of men over women (Bendels et al., 2018b; González-Alvarez & Sos-Peña, 2020; West et al., 2013).

Authorship position is a critical factor for research career prospects (Milojević et al., 2018). Collaborative papers with mixed authorship tend to be first-authored by men (Broderick & Casadevall, 2019), while the presence of women in the byline increases the likelihood of having a higher number of women co-authors (Aakhus et al., 2018; González-Alvarez & Sos-Peña, 2020; Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023; Zettler et al., 2017). For example, in Ecology and Zoology journals in Latin America, the presence of women in the byline depends strongly on the gender of the last author (Salerno et al., 2019). Women also face further constraints, as they are more likely to experience authorship disagreements, and men are more likely to determine authorship unilaterally (Ni et al., 2021). Additionally, women are less credited with authorship than men for the same type of contributions (Ross et al., 2022), resulting in a higher “time-to-credit payoff” and fewer publications during PhD stages (Feldon et al., 2017). Dissatisfaction with authorship attributions is related to the academic position and gender of authors (Smith et al., 2020). As the motivation to work in research teams may depend on perceived risks and gains (Feng & Kirkley, 2020), this devaluation of women’s work creates cumulative disadvantages in scientific careers, especially for early-career researchers (Fleming, 2021).

3.1.2 Productivity. Literature has focused extensively on the “productivity puzzle” (Abramo et al., 2009; Astegiano et al., 2019; Campbell & Simberloff, 2022; Ceci et al., 2014; Nakhaie, 2008; Xie & Shauman, 1998). Many studies find productivity gaps, which are field-specific (Duch et al., 2012) and most likely related to career length and dropouts (Huang et al., 2020). This difference in productivity typically appears from early career stages (Symonds et al., 2006) and across different publication types (Mayer & Rathmann, 2018).

There are many aspects that influence differences in productivity, such as career advancement (see 3.1.5) or differences in authorship (see 3.1.1), amongst many others. One such difference is specialization (Zeng et al., 2019). Women tend to publish in a

wider range of topics (Leahey, 2006), exhibit different publication patterns (Mayer & Rathmann, 2018) and perform a broader range of tasks. They engage more in teaching and administrative work than men and volunteer twice as often for non-promotable tasks (Vesterlund et al., 2014), a phenomenon known as “academic housework” (Heijstra et al., 2017). This leads to double discrimination in university recruitment processes (Brommesson et al., 2022), where women are expected to undertake more teaching and administrative tasks, which are then undervalued during evaluations.

3.1.3 Citations. Citations are one of the topics where we find less consensus. Citation differences vary by field and much attention has been paid to citations in STEM disciplines. The analysis by Kuchanskyi et al. (2023) focused mainly on STEM publications and showed that articles predominantly authored by men were cited more than those with more women authors. Additionally, Bendels et al. (2018b) found that articles in certain STEM categories of the Nature Index with key women authorships were cited less than those with key men authors. In Physics, publications authored by women are under-cited, while those authored by men tend to be over-cited (Teich et al., 2022), possibly because men started publishing earlier in their careers (Kong et al., 2022). Similarly, in Astronomy, papers written by women receive fewer citations than those written by men (Caplar et al., 2017).

Research has also focused on fields outside of STEM. For instance, the situation is unclear in the Life Sciences. Andersen et al. (2019) found almost no gender differences in citations in Medicine when adjusting for other variables. In contrast, Chatterjee & Werner (2021) reported that articles written by women published in high-impact medical journals were less cited than those by men. Although gender bias in citations is less common among younger scientists, it still contributes to making women’s research less visible in the life sciences (Zhou et al., 2024). Less research has been done on Social Sciences, Humanities and Arts. However, there is evidence that women are under-cited in fields such as International Relations (Maliniak et al., 2013) and Communication (Wang et al., 2021).

Citation behavior exhibits gender homophily as suggested by Teich et al. (2022) in their study of Contemporary Physics. In the field of Communication in Germany, men

cite other men more than women cite women (Potthoff & Zimmermann, 2017). In this sense, men's citation practices seem to contribute to the under-citation of women (Dion et al., 2018; Dworkin et al., 2020) and this gender homophily in citations has been found in most scientific fields (e.g. Ghiasi et al., 2018; Dehdarirad & Yaghtin, 2024). Moreover, it tends to prevail in every discipline when excluding self-citations and career gaps (Cameron et al., 2016). This could lead to an uninterrupted disparity since men tend to publish more during their careers (Wu, 2024).

Other variables taken into consideration are geography, productivity and career stage. Thelwall (2020) analyzed gender differences in six English speaking-countries showing that "[i]t is rare for field citation advantages to be dominated by one gender in a country" (p. 610). Chan & Torgler (2020) studied 21 fields in 43 countries, concluding that amongst top scholars, citation inequality was higher than productivity inequality. Regarding elite authors, results are somewhat contradictory: Aksnes et al. (2011) found fewer citation differences among the most productive researchers, while Ioannidis et al., (2023) reported significant citation differences among top-cited authors. Moreover, the role of career stage is closely linked to productivity (e.g. Ceci et al., 2014). Gender citation gaps are smaller at the early career stage and tend to increase with career progression, mirroring productivity between genders (Wu, 2023). Larivière et al. (2011) also noted this trend in Québec University, observing that, after the age of 38, women are disadvantaged in citations. Additionally, the experiment carried out by Huang et al. (2020) found no gender differences in citations when comparing men and women with equivalent careers.

Research on the role played by self-citations is also contradictory. Some studies found that men self-cite more than women (King et al., 2017) while others claimed the opposite (Caplar et al., 2017). Some reported no differences (Mishra et al., 2018) or have not found a positive impact of self-citations on career outcomes given gender (Azoulay & Lynn, 2020). At the same time, some encourage women to self-cite more (Cameron et al., 2016), while others believe this will not necessarily translate into scholarly gains (King et al., 2017).

3.1.4 Contributions. Research examines author contribution statements to investigate women's roles in research teams (Allen et al., 2019), but contributor role taxonomies are not widely implemented (Hosseini et al., 2023). Macaluso et al. (2016) found that women tend to perform experiments more frequently than men, a trend that remains constant throughout their scientific career. Women are more likely to carry out technical work and write the original draft, while men are more likely to review and edit the manuscript, acquire funding, provide resources and supervise projects (Larivière et al., 2021; Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023).

Gender inequalities among authors who made equal contributions raise concerns about women not receiving proper credit for publications, suggesting a need for journals to clarify the method used to determine author order (Broderick & Casadevall, 2019). Similarly, Paul-Hus et al. (2020) found that women are heavily underrepresented in the acknowledgement sections. These differences in role distribution affect women's career prospects, as they are less likely to be seen as leaders during early and middle career stages, which is crucial for long-term academic success (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020).

3.1.5 Academic rank and career advancement. It is assumed that gender parity in senior roles will happen as the number of women in academia increases (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023). However, the number of women progressing from tenure to full professorship has not "kept pace with their rise in numbers in academia" (Bonawitz & Anzel, 2009, p.2), and the number of women in academia reduces as we climb the career ladder. This phenomenon, known as the "leaky pipeline" (Corona-Sobrino et al., 2020; Mihaljević-Brandt et al., 2016; Spoon et al., 2023), sees women dropping out of academia as they progress, with many of them leaving right after graduate school (Mengel et al., 2019) and not reaching seniority (Aramayona et al., 2022).

Even before early-career stages, differences exist among bachelor's students and doctoral candidates. There seems to be a trend where gender parity among students is diminishing, especially in STEM. Evidence shows that the growth of women graduating is slowing down, as seen in Mathematics in Spain (Aramayona et al., 2022) or Computer Science in the United States (Sherman, 2015). Research finds a similar picture among

PhDs: gender parity was reached by the 2010s, but since then, women have become underrepresented again (Sánchez-Jiménez et al., 2023).

Once students become researchers, these differences persist. For instance, although men tend to leave more academia at their early career stage than at any other stage (Xing et al., 2019), women's dropout rates as early-career scientists are higher (e.g. Jadidi et al., 2018; Isphording & Qendrai, 2019). Research indicates that women may leave academia not only for work-life balance reasons but also due to the work environment, which does not affect men in the same way (Levine et al., 2011; Spoon et al., 2023). Huang et al. (2020) conclude that higher dropout rates may explain differences found in productivity and impact. Given their striking numbers, most research on dropouts has focused on STEM disciplines (Cech & Blair-Loy, 2019; Cundiff et al., 2013; Jadidi et al., 2018; Mihaljević-Brandt et al., 2016).

Collaborative patterns and evaluative practices in promotion seem to be gendered (Fox, 2020) and collaboration affects men and women's career prospects differently. For women, their co-authors' gender influences their probability of receiving tenure, but it does not affect men equally (Sarsons, 2017). This picture is less clear when discussing evaluative practices: a higher presence of women in evaluation panels has been associated with higher success rates for women applying for full professorships (Zinovyeva & Bagues, 2011). However, Williams & Ceci (2015) found the opposite in men-dominated fields, where women had a greater chance for promotion.

3.1.6 Journals. Gender studies examining journals have followed a twofold objective. Firstly, to look at the (under)representation of women in authorship bylines, and secondly, to analyze women's presence on editorial boards. Following the first approach, research finds that women are underrepresented in high-impact journals (Mauleón et al., 2013; Shen et al., 2018), even in fields dominated by women (Squazzoni et al., 2021). This underrepresentation is partly because women often engage in topics that receive less attention from these outlets (Light, 2013) and their work tends to receive less favorable peer review scores (Fox et al., 2018).

Women's representation is also alarmingly low among journal editors, who are key players in the scientific communication system (Kennedy et al., 2001). This low

presence extends to editorial boards across many disciplines (Aiston & Jung, 2015; Liu et al., 2023b; Metz & Harzing, 2009). For instance, in most Psychology and Neuroscience journals, more than half of editors were men in 2019 (Palser et al., 2022). In top-ranked medical journals, women comprised around 16% of editors-in-chief (Amrein et al., 2011). Women on editorial boards are less likely to be editor-in-chief, and more likely to perform administrative tasks (Burg et al., 2022). The progressive reduction in women's participation when moving up the career ladder does not explain these differences entirely, as the proportion of women editors is lower than their representation in senior faculty positions (Fishman et al., 2017).

3.1.7 Conferences. Women are underrepresented in scientific conferences and workshops (Santosa et al., 2019), where the presence of the so-called "manels" (all-men panels) is still common. Women do not present their work at conferences as much as their counterparts, regardless of their work being of higher quality (Housri et al., 2008). There has been an improvement in overall parity (Ruzycki et al., 2019), and the presence of women within the organization or in panels increases the proportion of women participants (Casadevall & Handelsman, 2014; Nittrouer et al., 2018; Sardelis & Drew, 2016; Zaza et al., 2021). However, even when there is overall parity, men gather more attention in terms of participation than women: they ask more questions (Carter et al., 2018), take more time during their interventions (Jones et al., 2014), and men's lectures receive higher attendance (Aufenvenne et al., 2021). Furthermore, women prefer presenting posters instead of talks, while men prefer the opposite (Isbell et al., 2012).

3.2 Explicative factors for the gender gap in academia

The literature also seeks to identify factors contributing to these differences. This section is structured around three main aspects. Firstly, we examine gendered behavioral patterns and preferences, which encompass gender homophily and preferences for one gender over another in quality perceptions, collaborative choices, evaluation processes and topic selection. Secondly, we explore gender roles in science, looking into differences in research strategies, workload and work-life balance. Lastly, we focus on gendered impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.2.1 Gendered preferences. Science shows gendered preferences, which manifest as either gender homophily (a preference for one's gender) or a generalized bias favoring men over women. These generalized preferences are evident in various aspects such as quality perception, collaboration, evaluative processes or research interests.

Gender homophily is especially noticeable in collaboration choices. Regardless of seniority or the proportion of women in Life Sciences disciplines, men and women often prefer to collaborate with the same gender (Holman & Morandin, 2019; Prakash et al., 2024). Women may exhibit a stronger gender homophily (Jadidi et al., 2018), but will more often be part of mixed teams, while men have a greater propensity to collaborate in male-only teams (Kwiek & Roszka, 2021). Homophily is also observed in peer review processes. Studies of journals such as *eLife* (Murray et al., 2018), *Frontiers* (Helmer et al., 2017) and the *American Political Science Review* (König & Ropers, 2022) show that both men and women rate more favorably work conducted by colleagues from their own gender. This effect can be minimized in mixed-gender peer review groups (König & Ropers, 2022). In the case of citations, gender homophily may be linked to differences in some research areas (Potthoff & Zimmermann, 2017). Lastly, women's presence at scientific gatherings also reflects gender homophily (see section 3.1.7).

In the absence of gender homophily, men will be preferred over women. This may be due to perceptions that men's work is of higher quality (Knobloch-Westerwick et al., 2013) or harder to produce. For example, women doctoral students are perceived as less committed to their work (Ellemers et al., 2004). Additionally, gender biases lead to women scholars being miss-cited as men significantly more often than the reverse (Krawczyk, 2017). Despite this, research shows that women's work exhibits either higher quality (Housri et al., 2008) or no significant quality difference (Lewison, 2001) with that of their counterparts. In fact, gender-mixed teams often produce better quality science (Campbell et al., 2013; Nielsen, et al., 2017a).

This preference for men over women is also observed in collaboration. For example, Whittington (2018) reported that both, men and women, tended to collaborate more with men in biotechnology patents. Men are seen as more attractive collaborators in male-typed topics, and vice versa (Knobloch-Westerwick et al., 2013). These

preferences can vary significantly across disciplines (Yamamoto & Frachtenberg, 2022; Zeng et al., 2016).

A field for contested findings is that of evaluative processes to obtain funding. Although gender differences are also observed in grant evaluation processes, the literature is unable to confirm if gender preferences are affecting grant allocation. Cruz-Castro et al. (2022) reviewed the literature and concluded that the variability in national contexts made a comprehensive global picture elusive. A meta-analysis of 21 studies indicated that men have a 7% higher probability of grant approval than women (Bornmann et al., 2007). However, Marsh et al. (2009), found no significant gender differences using the same data. Country-specific studies reveal mixed outcomes: in Italy, men are more likely to succeed (Bagues et al., 2014; Jappelli et al., 2017; Bellotti et al., 2022), while in Quebec, women over 38 receive less funding than men (Larivière et al., 2011). In Canada, principal investigator women are evaluated less favorably (Witteman et al., 2019). The Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research experiences a 4% loss of women during grant review (Van der Lee & Ellemers, 2015). Larregue & Nielsen (2024) suggest that funding differences may stem from gendered topic selections, with quantitative research often deemed more robust and receiving more funding, and Liao & Lian (2024) found that the so-called “halo effect” on funding is affected by gender.

Gender also affects research interests and topic selection. The “people-versus-things” dichotomy shows that women are more likely to study people-related topics like Nursing or Psychology, while men prefer things-related topics like Engineering or Mathematics (Ceci et al., 2014). This trend takes place across most countries. Charles & Bradley (2009) found that countries with higher economic indicators exhibit larger gender gaps in STEM fields. Similarly, Stoet & Geary (2018) found that democratization of higher education does not correlate with a reduction in gendered discipline choices. Kozlowski et al. (2022) showed that minoritized researchers often study topics related to their gendered or racialized identities. Interdisciplinary research is also gendered, with women more likely to engage in it (Rhoten & Pfirman, 2007; Pinheiro et al., 2022).

3.2.2 Gendered roles and work-life balance. The roles researchers play are gendered, with men and women developing different research strategies. Women are often directed toward teaching and administrative tasks, while men reserve more time for research (Filandri & Pasqua, 2021). Despite these differences, student evaluations tend to favor men (MacNeill et al., 2015; Mengel et al., 2019; Miller & Chamberlin, 2000). Furthermore, an overemphasis on publications during evaluations devalues teaching and administrative tasks, thereby hindering women's career progression (Hatch & Curry, 2020; van den Brink & Benschop, 2012). Moreover, women are less likely to attain leadership roles during early and mid-career stages (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020).

Studies also look into differences in researchers' work-life balance (Kyvik & Teigen, 1996; O'Brien & Hapgood, 2012). Women often undertake more domestic chores and caregiving responsibilities, leaving less time for research (Kalra et al., 2023). This "parenting penalty" (Derrick et al., 2022) affects women's productivity (Hunter & Leahey, 2010). Although the "productivity penalty" is decreasing (Morgan et al., 2021), parenthood still affects women's career prospects more negatively than men's (Zheng et al., 2022). Even when tasks are reportedly divided equally, women researchers often engage more in parenting activities (Derrick et al., 2022). Conversely, some studies suggest that the presence of children can increase productivity for both genders, possibly due to a "positive self-selection effect" where only the most productive women manage both roles (Fox, 2005; Joecks et al., 2014).

This gendered work-life balance affects mobility, with women being less mobile than men (Lubitow & Zippel, 2014; Tower & Latimer, 2016; Jöns, 2011; Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023). Women will move geographically closer to home and to fewer countries (Moguérrou, 2004; Zhao et al., 2023). Underrepresentation in international mobility is especially pronounced in Physical Sciences (Momeni et al., 2022), and women often move internationally when their caring responsibilities are lower (Cañibano et al., 2016). Moving with partners seems more challenging than moving with children (Zippel, 2011) and having a partner may have a stronger impact on women's mobility decisions than on men's (Rivera, 2017; Uhly et al., 2015). Consequently, there is a call for "gender-aware" policies rather than "gender-neutral" ones (Burch et al., 2023).

This lower international presence impacts collaboration, with men collaborating more internationally than women (Aksnes et al., 2019; González-Álvarez & Cervera-Crespo, 2017). Women rely more on national funds and receive less international funding (Ruggieri et al., 2021). Abramo et al. (2019) observed that in Italy these differences are reduced among highly productive authors.

3.2.3 Gendered impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. This gendered work-life balance picture is exacerbated by extraordinary events like the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic has accentuated existing gender disparities in work-life balance (Andersen et al., 2020; Bell & Fong, 2021; Ribarovska et al., 2021). Some studies suggest there were no significant gender differences in publication rates during the pandemic (Abramo et al., 2022; Jemielniak et al., 2022). However, women had a generally lower contribution to COVID-19 research (Vincent-Lamarre et al., 2020), with a noticeable decrease in overall productivity, especially among mid-career women (Kwon et al., 2023). Women's leadership, as indicated by first-authored publications, also declined (Liu et al., 2022). Additionally, research on COVID-19 often overrepresented male patients (Salter-Volz et al., 2021).

3.3 Consequences

This review unveils a nuanced landscape with significant negative repercussions, which we categorize into two distinct sections: career diversity within the scientific workforce, and balanced and inclusive generation of scientific knowledge. These consequences restrict career prospects and opportunities for women and have detrimental effects on the direction of research, impeding diverse scientific outputs and innovations, and perpetuating gender inequality.

3.3.1. Career diversity and scientific workforce. Every element discussed here creates a vicious circle that negatively affects women's careers (Aiston & Jung, 2015; Freund et al., 2016). This cycle results in fewer opportunities, lower retention rates, and hindered career progression for women, contributing to the accumulation of disadvantages known as Matilda effect (Rossiter, 1993). This leads to different career trajectories, successes and transitions (Filandri & Pasqua, 2021; Jagsi et al., 2011; Lerchenmueller & Sorenson, 2018). Women face more difficulties entering informal

networks within the scientific community, with “workplace climate” being one of the top reasons for women leaving academia (Spoon et al., 2023). This is related to the existence of daily “micro-inequities” (Aiston & Fo, 2020).

Women’s careers are generally shorter and there are more gaps in their publishing careers compared to men. Women and men experience diverse career lengths (Huang et al., 2020), although differences in productivity cannot be solely explained by career length or stage, but also by the number of men and women starting careers as researchers (Boekhout et al., 2021). These restraints on gender diversity also affect the scientific workforce as a whole. Diversity – whether gender, ethnic or geographical diversity – leads to more novel research, is better for problem-solving (Nielsen et al., 2017a), generates higher impact (Yang et al., 2022) and receives more citations (Powell, 2018).

3.3.2 Balanced and inclusive generation of scientific knowledge. The literature highlights two main elements related to gender and the generation of new knowledge. First, the lack of gender diversity leads to biased research outcomes and less innovative findings. All-women and mixed teams tend to include variables of sex and gender in their research more than all-men teams (Key & Sumner, 2019). There is a strong positive correlation between women’s authorship and the probability of a study including gender and sex analysis (Nielsen et al., 2017b). This is relevant because sex inclusion, analysis and reporting can change the conclusions of an investigation (Sugimoto et al., 2019), and extrapolating data from one sex to another can be dangerous (Klein et al., 2015).

Second, some disciplines and topics are dominated by a specific gender and there tends to be homophily between authors’ demographics and the topics they research (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023). Kozlowski et al. (2022) develop the idea of “privilege of choice”, where the choice of a particular topic is influenced by gender and race. In the US, men tend to study STEM topics, whereas women are more likely to study topics more related to Gender-Based Violence, Families, Learning, LGBT Studies and Nursing (Kozlowski et al., 2022). Stereotypes are considered more impactful than discrimination in some fields, influencing women’s absence in certain disciplines because they do not enter them in the first place (Ceci et al., 2014).

Moreover, when women enter fields previously dominated by men, there is often a “reconfiguration” of segregation (Acker, 2006). For instance, in Medicine, women tend to specialize in Pediatrics, Gynecology and General Practice, but not in Surgery, which remains dominated by men (Acker, 2006; Alers et al., 2014). In Library and Information Science, women are overrepresented in human and health themes, while men are more predominant in STEM-related themes (Choji et al., 2024).

4. Discussion

This paper provides a comprehensive narrative review of bibliometric studies on gender inequalities within the academic system. We first review methodological aspects of these studies. Gender is commonly assigned based on bibliographic metadata, mainly author names and in some cases, affiliation data. However, this has its shortcomings. Firstly, gender assignment algorithms assume we can determine gender from names, disregarding the fact that names do not necessarily correlate with gender. Secondly, they reflect a binary vision of gender (a name is either "male" or "female"). Thirdly, these processes do not work well for all countries of origin and language, leading to inaccuracies and hindering reproducibility.

Bibliometric studies analyze gender differences using different units of analysis which impede or at least difficult comparability and generalization of findings. The most common units of analysis used are publications, while individual researchers are the one less used. This may be due to the complexity of using other units of analysis than publications. Since results vary depending on the unit of analysis used, we may be missing important information by underusing some of them. The point which remains more critical or controversial is that of explaining the mechanisms behind such differences. Do they respond to actual gender biases? Are there causal mechanisms that could be rectified? Although these issues may respond more to methodological limitations than to an absence of causes, finding the necessary evidence to demonstrate that these differences respond to actual inequalities and are not of natural order seem to still be needed (Ball et al., 2021, Andersen et al., 2021).

Gender differences are found in almost every aspect of academia, reflecting the social inequalities present outside the research world. However, the attention received to such differences has been unequal in the literature. Most papers reviewed focus on authorship, productivity and citations. On the other hand, issues such as contributions, career advancement or journal boards composition, still need to be further investigated, beyond merely descriptive methods. This may be due to data availability or the complexity added by introducing other elements such as career length or gaps.

The reasons attributed to gender differences are varied and interrelated. There is a high consensus in the literature with regard to the existence of gender homophily (Jadidi et al., 2018), gendered topic selection (Kozłowski et al., 2022) and gendered parenting penalty (Derrick et al., 2022). Conversely, there is less consensus in relation to funding allocation and other elements such as collaboration preferences. These reasons have negative effects on women's career progression (Aiston & Jung, 2015), who face more barriers than men with regard to informal networking (Spoon et al., 2023) and opportunities for mobility (Tower & Latimer, 2016), creating a 'ceiling glass' which impedes them to reach senior positions in academia (Bonawitz & Andel, 2009).

This is challenging, not only for women, but for the sustainability of a healthy and diverse scientific ecosystem. There is evidence on the relation between the diversity of scientists and better problem-solving (Nielsen et al., 2017a) or citation impact (Yang et al., 2022; Powell, 2018). Furthermore, there are gendered preferences on the direction research takes or the variables considered in a study, which ensure the relevance and pertinence of new scientific knowledge (Key & Summer, 2019; Sugimoto et al., 2019). The consequences of gender inequality of science transcend therefore women researchers and can backlash to society.

5. Future agenda and concluding remarks

Overall, we find several weaknesses in the literature that can be further explored. These are reported in Table 2. Some of these relate to current limitations such as the opacity of some studies using proprietary gender assignment algorithms (e.g., Gender API, Genderize.io) or their lack of coverage for certain regions (e.g., Asian names). Others

relate to the need to establish a comparative framework to integrate findings from different studies, such as explicitly mentioning the unit of analysis used or expanding the analysis to non-Western countries which are underrepresented in the current literature.

Table 2. Opportunities for improvement and potential directions for research

Theme	Potential directions/improvements
Accuracy and coverage of gender assignment algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of open data sources and reproducibility of algorithms - Improvements on geographic coverage
Comparability of studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explicit reporting and transparency on units of analysis - Expand analyses to non-Western countries - Expand analyses to more fields than STEM
Understudied topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender differences in research funding - Gender differences in team dynamics and contributor roles - Gender differences on topic selection
Interpretability and context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used of mixed-methods approaches to improve the interpretability of findings - Reporting of context-specific case studies

Other weaknesses identified refer to the need to focus on aspects that have been understudied either due to methodological limitations (e.g., bibliometric identification of research funding) or data availability (e.g., contribution statements data). Research funding data is generally difficult to obtain and to attribute to specific individuals due to limitations in the bibliometric data and privacy concerns, although data integration with external data sources could improve this line of research. Contribution data could potentially dig into the social mechanisms that affect author order and the distribution of credit (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020), offering the opportunity to dig into the ways gender differences emerge from the social organization of the sciences.

Finally, we find issues related to interpretability and the need to contextualize findings. So far, most studies try to provide a global perspective on the gender gap. However, in many cases differences in gender can be better understood and interpreted

through the lenses of specific case studies and contexts. In this regard, there is the opportunity to blend bibliometric approaches with other methodologies that can help contextualize findings and provide key insights into the mechanisms by which gender differences arise.

This review pinpoints issues and themes that emerge across bibliometric research on gender differences in science. Studies on women's disadvantages have moved beyond the confines of traditional feminist frameworks, entering other spheres of research and fostering a needed interdisciplinary engagement (Shokida et al., 2024). Still, within bibliometrics, research needs some conceptual clarity, as they still tend to mix basic concepts such as sex and gender and acknowledge gender as a spectrum rather than binary.

Persistent gender disadvantages still require attention and action. We acknowledge the challenging nature of this future research agenda. Data is often not ideal, and establishing causality is difficult. However, we hope this review stimulates further opportunities to reduce gender inequality. Addressing these issues and developing critical reflections on them is crucial to avoid "gender fatigue" (Kelan, 2009) and enable progress. By embracing new methodologies and perspectives, we can ensure that all previous work contributes to broader social understanding and creates lasting value in the field of gender studies. It is a socially responsible act for producing more nuanced and beneficial research.

Notes

[1] Throughout this literature review, we use women/men to refer to gender and rather than female/male. Quoted articles are not modified, therefore some of them may not follow this guideline.

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